

**PRINTED AND AUDIO-VISUAL AIDED MODULAR LEARNING
DELIVERIES IN RELATION TO STUDENTS'
PERFORMANCE IN SCIENCE 10**

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Printed and Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Deliveries in Relation to Students' Performance in Science 10

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Abstract

The quasi-experimental study has reported for the first time the benefits of a learning delivery modality where Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD) was upgraded to Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD) in order to level up students' performance in Science. This aimed to compare the students' performance in Science 10 utilizing PMLD and AMLD. The population of ninety ($n = 90$) student-participants at Lebak National High School were divided into two groups - under PMLD as control and under AMLD as experimental. The performances of students were assessed through the pre-test and post-test questionnaires while the motivation and interest of the AMLD group of students were determined through a survey questionnaire. The difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the students in the two groups was assessed using the t-Test. Then, descriptive analysis was employed to ascertain the values students had obtained from the audio-visual-assisted modular instruction in Science 10. Both control (PMLD) and experimental (AMLD) groups show poor performance in the pre-test and average performance in the post-test. The post-test performance of the students under PMLD does not differ significantly from the performance of the students under the AMLD. The utilization of audio-visual aids (AMLD) in learning Science 10, particularly on the topics of mirror and lenses, has not demonstrated an advantage over the PMLD. However, the AMLD students' motivation and interest are both high with the utilization of audio-visual aids with the modular learning delivery.

Keywords: *printed module, audio-visual aid, student performance, learning deliveries, science 10*

Introduction

Students' performance in science was the formal focus of the curriculum in the 1850s by the British Educational System (DeBoer, 1991) and in the 1950s in the Philippines when introduced by the American public school system (Caoli, 1986). It has faced several challenges over the years as learning delivery systems have undergone a few improvements designed to address shifting societal contexts and related issues, such as dealing with the challenges of a growing population, the economy, and communicable diseases (DeBoer, 1991). However, students' performance internationally has gained the poorest performance based on the result of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2018). During the COVID-19 pandemic, students' performance in science has been facing a worse scenario, even with the onset of various distance learning modalities.

Out of all the different distance learning modalities, the modular approach is the most popular since it offers tailored instruction and lets students employ self-learning modules in paper or digital format, depending on what is appropriate for them (Llego, 2021). Due to numerous activities, distractions, and lack of attention in today's world, it faces a few difficulties, including self-studying, inadequate internet connections, lack of sleep, and time to complete all modules (Davis, 2021). The delivery of modular learning seems to benefit students' performance despite the difficulties (Aksan, 2021). There has been no research on enhancing the modular learning delivery method with audio-visual modalities.

Audio-visual resources have historically restricted instruction to a teacher-centered model in which students take a passive role (Ojobor, Babarinde, & Fagbemi, 2020). It has a reputation for being alluring and maintaining students' enthusiasm and interest (Ibe & Abamu, 2019). Nevertheless, students' performance suffered due to its inadequate use and poor utilization (Shamsideen, 2016). Last academic year, its underutilization, particularly in Science 10, was indicative of the pupils at Lebak National High School's poor performance in the general scholastic average, which was just 84% and was defined as being on the verge of proficiency (Department of Education, 2012). To improve student performance, particularly in Science 10, the current study takes on audio-visual assistance in improving modular learning delivery modality.

Research Questions

This study aims to compare the students' performance in Science 10 utilizing Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD) and Audio-Visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD). Specifically, it aims to:

1. determine the test performances of students that receive Printed Modular Learning Delivery;
2. determine the test performances of students that receive Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery;
3. compare the pre-test performances between the students with PMLD and those with AMLD;
4. compare the post-test performances between the students with PMLD and those with AMLD; and,
5. determine the responses of the students in using AMLD in learning Science 10, in terms of motivation and interest.

Literature Review

This section discusses the literature and research that has been done in the past that is relevant to the current study, or that it is related to in some way. This provided the author with sufficient context for comprehending the study.

Students' Performance in Science

The performance of the students is crucial in creating the greatest graduates who will serve as outstanding leaders and laborers for the nation and thus oversee the nation's economic and social growth (Ali et al., 2009). It is regarded as the cornerstone in the Philippines for the curricular changes made to the scientific education to provide students a better understanding of how the topics they study in class relate to actual circumstances (Tan, 2007). The students' performance in science country-wide, despite the Department of Education's attention, has been deteriorating as reflected by very low students' performance in Science to some of the international standard examinations like the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2018. In this assessment, the Philippines scored among the lowest in reading, mathematics, and science than the countries which participated in the assessment. The said assessment was given to fifteen-year-old students in randomly selected schools in participating countries (OECD, 2018).

Meanwhile, in Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) last 2019, the students in the Philippines were labeled worst for scoring the lowest in the said assessment among the 58 countries involved in the study (CNN, 2020; Villegas, 2021). This later information intensifies and validates the results of PISA 2018.

Additionally, according to the National Achievement Test (NAT) scores from 2019, children have the lowest levels of competency in Science, Math, and English (Malipot, 2019). This NAT was given to children in grades 6, 10, and 12 throughout all schools in the nation. Furthermore, a study showed that the general weighted average (GWA) of students after the modular learning delivery during the outburst of the COVID-19 pandemic had decreased by 2.25% compared to their previous performances (Dargo & Dimas, 2021). In essence, it was advised that modules be streamlined together with video lectures and audio recordings, the conduct of online mediations, neighborhood training, and home visits to address the loops and eventually improve students' academic performance.

Printed Modular Learning Modality

The usage of printed modular materials was introduced by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines to ensure that learning would continue, particularly for students lacking internet connectivity. This approach became increasingly vital during the COVID-19 pandemic when traditional learning methods faced significant disruptions. Printed modules provide a tangible alternative, allowing students to engage with educational content in a structured manner.

This modality is not unique to the Philippines; it is also employed in countries like the USA and Australia, where similar challenges have arisen (Valencia, 2020). In these contexts, printed materials are designed to meet the diverse educational needs of children and maintain consistency in cognitive development. Research has shown that such materials can enhance learning outcomes by offering flexibility and accessibility, especially for marginalized students (Kirkwood & Price, 2020).

Compared to traditional approaches, using printed modules has yielded many benefits and demonstrated a positive impact on students' academic achievement. By enabling students to interact with information at their own pace, modular learning has been shown to improve students' comprehension of difficult topics (Valencia, 2020; Aksan, 2021; Lumanta et al., 2022). Students can revisit difficult subjects until they get them thanks to this flexibility, which can accommodate a variety of learning styles.

Moreover, as students frequently finish homework on their own, using printed modules helps them build a sense of responsibility (Talimodao & Madrigal, 2021). Apart from promoting responsibility, this self-guided method also fosters critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, which are crucial for continuous education. The skills that students acquire include time management, goal-setting, and self-assessment of their knowledge of the subject.

However, the results of a non-structured interview revealed that many students encountered significant obstacles and hardships in completing tasks and adhering to the directions provided in the module's learning activities (Bustillo & Aguilos, 2022). Common challenges identified include issues with internet access, which can severely limit engagement with the learning materials. Additionally, students reported insufficient learning resources, which hampers their ability to fully understand the content.

A lack of clarity in the module's instructions—often due to inadequate explanations and vague assessment procedures—was another critical concern. Students expressed confusion regarding expectations, leading to frustration and decreased motivation (Rotas & Cahapay, 2020). Furthermore, an unfavorable learning environment, characterized by distractions at home and insufficient support from family, complicates the learning process.

The overwhelming volume of remote learning tasks also posed a challenge, with many students struggling to balance their academic responsibilities with home activities. This conflict can lead to stress and burnout, exacerbating mental health issues that many students already face (Baticulon et al., 2021; Talimodao & Madrigal, 2021). Addressing these challenges is essential for enhancing the effectiveness of modular learning and supporting students' academic success.

Audio-visual Aid

Audio-visual materials (aids) simultaneously appeal to the senses of sight and hearing. It supports keeping students' interests alive and well (Ibe & Abamu, 2019). To minimize the gaps in learning when introducing abstract ideas, the usage of audio-visual aid could provide an initial background of the vague concept (Shivali, 2022). A study among high school students revealed that the use of Video-aided Instruction (VAI) in Physics significantly improved the students' performance ($p=0.000$ and $t=-8.233$) (Mastur, 2019). Similar results showed that students receiving audio-visual aids to education outperformed those receiving traditional instruction (Lapada & Lapada, 2017).

However, some disadvantages of the use of audio-visual aids have been noted. One of these is the availability of equipment capable of projecting audio-visual aid like smart and android phones, television, and LCD projector leading to the expense of utilizing audio-visual aids. Another is the stability of electricity in the area, especially since there are still some areas in the country that are off the grid. Also, the limited topic that can be studied in the audio-visual aid, its accuracy, innovativeness, and the medium of instruction could be factors in the effective and efficient utilization of audio-visual aid in learning (Balan & Chande, 2019).

Learning Deliveries

The Department of instruction has designed numerous learning modes to be able to provide pupils with the right instruction during the pandemic and cover learning in time. These learning styles include homeschooling, blended learning, and distance learning. Modular Distance Learning (MDL), which is available in print or digital form, TV-Radio Based Instruction, and Online Distance Learning are the other three categories under which distance learning is further categorized.

Instead of face-to-face classes, DepEd is implementing distance learning at the basic education level amidst the pandemic. Among the modalities posed by the department Modular Distance Learning in printed format is prominently used, especially by the public schools in the country (Maliput, 2020) with 82.0% preference and 39.3% usage. For private schools, ODL is the most preferred (41.3% usage).

Motivation and Interest in Learning

The interest in learning represents a student's cognitive aptitude for success in the sciences (Alhadabi, 2021). Urhahne and Wijnia (2023) provide an integrative framework for understanding motivation in education, reinforcing the idea that nurturing student interest is essential for cognitive success in the sciences. Together, these studies underscore the importance of fostering interest as a pathway to academic achievement. The more enthusiastic a learner is in science, the greater his or her dedication and desire to perform will surely lead to academic success. In a study, the integration of technology in the teaching-learning process, such as that of the audio-visual aid, is a motivating element potentially improving education (Al Aqad, Al-Saggaf, & Muthmainnah, 2021). Similarly, significantly meaningful experiences about the subject matter develop positive outlook and attitudes toward learning and understanding of the critical concepts in science as found by an earlier study (Harackiewicz, Durik, Barron, Garcia, & Tauer, 2017).

However, if there is a desire to learn but not enough motivation to engage in multiple educational endeavors, one does not develop the necessary skills and competencies, or if motivation is unsteady, then achieving the best academic performance may not be probable (Lamb, Annetta, Meldrum, & Vallet, 2011).

Methodology

This section presents the methodologies used to gather relevant data and analysis. These include the research design, study location, participants, sampling technique, data-gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study employs a quasi-experimental design to effectively compare the performances of students in the PMLD group with those in the AMLD group. This design is justified as it allows for a controlled examination of the outcomes without random assignment, which may not be feasible in educational settings. By utilizing existing groups, the study can focus on the natural variations in performance and learning outcomes influenced by different instructional strategies. This approach also enables a more practical analysis of motivation and interest developed from the introduction of audio-visual aid in modular learning.

Participants

The participants of this study were the ninety (90) officially enrolled Grade 10 students at Lebak National High School for School Year 2022-2023.

Instruments

The pre-test and post-test questionnaires focused on the subject matter from Weeks 7 to 9 of Quarter 2, in line with the Department of Education's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC). Questions were adapted from Student Learning Materials and categorized to assess students' knowledge, understanding, and process skills.

A survey was also developed to evaluate students' prior knowledge prior to the introduction of the audio-visual aided modular learning

delivery and the benefits gained from it. Utilizing a five-point Likert Scale, the survey measured motivation and interest as follows:

- 5 - Extremely motivated/interested;
- 4 - Highly motivated/interested;
- 3 - Moderately motivated/interested;
- 2 - Slightly motivated/interested; and
- 1 - Least motivated/interested

Procedure

Ninety (90) diverse learner-participants, representing various backgrounds and abilities, were systematically divided into two groups for this study: the PMLD (control) group and the AMLD (experimental) group. To establish a baseline for learning, a pre-test was administered to both groups, measuring their initial understanding of the subject matter.

The PMLD group engaged with the modules independently, studying and completing the assigned tasks without any external support or intervention. In contrast, the AMLD group received enhanced learning assistance through a teacher-crafted audio-visual aid, which was displayed on a flat-screen LED TV in the classroom. This visual and auditory resource aimed to enrich their learning experience, providing context and facilitating comprehension as they navigated through the module activities.

Upon completing the two sets of modules, all participants took a post-test to assess their knowledge gains. The data from both the pre-test and post-test were meticulously gathered, totaled, and tabulated. Subsequently, thorough analysis and interpretation were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the audio-visual aid and its impact on student learning outcomes compared to the independent study approach. This comprehensive analysis aimed to draw meaningful conclusions about the potential benefits of integrating multimedia resources in educational settings.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviation were utilized as descriptive statistics together with other statistical tools to characterize the pre-test and post-test results. The difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the students in the two groups was assessed using the t-Test. Then, descriptive analysis was employed to ascertain the values students had obtained from the audio-visual-assisted modular instruction in science 10.

Results and Discussion

In this section the results of the study are presented and discussed with reference to the aim of the study, which was to compare the students' performance in Science 10 utilizing Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD) and Audio-Visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD).

Test Performances of Students in Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD)

The test performances based on the number of students that obtained correct answers in the Science 10 pre-test and post-test under the Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD) are presented in Table 1. Table 1. *Test performances based on the number of students that obtain correct answers in the Science 10 pre-test and post-test under the Printed Modular Learning Delivery (n = 45)*

Test Statement	Items	Correct Answers			
		No. of Students, F	Pretest %f	No. of Students, F	Post Test %f
KNOWLEDGE					
Regular reflection is the <u>even</u> reflection of light on a(n) <u>smooth</u> surface.		36	80%	39	87%
A plane mirror has a <u>flat</u> reflecting surface.		11	24%	27	60%
As per the Law of Reflection measured through the normal line, the angle of incidence is <u>equal</u> to the angle of reflection.		30	67%	29	64%
A type of lens that is thicker at the center as compared to its edges is <u>convex</u> .		13	29%	23	51%
A type of lens curves inward toward its center is <u>concave</u> .		6	13%	25	56%
The type of image formed by concave lenses (is) <u>always virtual</u> .		8	18%	19	42%
An application of multiple image reflection is <u>kaleidoscope</u> .		9	20%	21	47%
A type of lens is used in a magnifying glass is <u>converging lens</u> .		10	22%	22	49%
The part of the camera that corresponds to the retina of our eyes is <u>photographic film</u> .		13	29%	17	38%
Convex lenses are used in <u>all of the above</u> .		9	20%	18	40%
Mean		14.5	32%	24	53%
UNDERSTANDING					
The image you see on a plane mirror is placed in the <u>opposite</u> direction(s) of real image.		14	31%	22	49%

Diffuse Reflection is a(n) <u>uneven</u> reflection of light rays on a <u>rough</u> surface.	10	22%	20	44%
Scattering of light occurs when light waves travelling in <u>one</u> direction is made to travel in <u>many</u> direction(s).	11	24%	20	44%
With Regular Reflection, the <u>angle and surface</u> of the object will determine the sharpness of reflection.	15	33%	23	51%
The image formed in a plane mirror is <u>at the same distance behind the mirror with the object</u> .	14	31%	16	36%
A typical mirror you look in at home is a <u>plane</u> mirror.	30	67%	22	49%
A type of lens that is used to correct nearsightedness is <u>concave</u> .	15	33%	24	53%
A concave lens is used by <u>magnifying glasses</u> .	8	18%	14	31%
A type of mirror that is used in the side mirrors of cars to give the driver a wider area and smaller image of traffic behind him is <u>convex mirror</u> .	9	20%	26	58%
A car's headlight uses <u>concave mirror</u> .	14	31%	22	49%
Mean	14	31%	20.9	46%
PROCESS				
A concave mirror may form an image which is <u>real, inverted, and diminished</u> .	7	16%	13	29%
The image in a convex mirror is always <u>virtual, erect, and diminished</u> .	11	24%	11	24%
A type of lens that produces smaller and upright images is <u>concave lens</u> .	9	20%	18	40%
The size of the image is always smaller than the object in <u>convex mirror</u> .	10	22%	21	47%
You see the reflection of the analog type of clock without numbers in your plane mirror. If the image formed by the hands of the clock shows the time of 8:30, then is the real time is <u>3:30</u> .	10	22%	14	31%
A mirror concept that explains why the word AMBULANCE is written in reverse in an ambulance car is <u>lateral inversion</u> .	6	13%	24	53%
Concave mirror produces <u>smaller image</u> .	9	20%	20	44%
The sun's rays are observed to focus at a point behind a lens. The type of lens used is <u>converging lens</u> .	12	27%	14	31%
A type of image is formed by the concave side of the spoon when the object is closer to it is <u>upside down and smaller</u> .	3	7%	13	29%
The letter "e" that appears in the mirror as _____ . \ominus _____	28	62%	36	80%
Mean	10.5	23%	18.4	41%

In the pre-test, the number of students that obtain correct answers in Science 10 is highest at 14.5 for Knowledge, followed by 14 for Understanding, and 10.5 for Process. In the post-test, a similar trend although with higher values, the number of students with the correct answers is highest at 24 for Knowledge, followed by 20.9 for Understanding, and 18.4 for Process. The post-test performances appear to have the highest net increase from the pre-tests at 53 % for Knowledge, 46 % for Understanding, and 41 % Process for. Generally, there are net increments in these 3 behavioral levels.

The summary of students' performance in the pre-test and post-test in Science 10 under the Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of students' performance in pre-test and post-test under the Printed Modular Learning Delivery (PMLD) (n=45)

Scores	Verbal Description	Pre-test Scores		Post-test Scores	
		F	f%	F	f%
0-12	Poor	41	91.11%	20	44.44%
13-18	Average	4	8.89%	15	33.33%
19-24	High	0	0%	10	22.22%
25-30	Very High	0	0%	0	0%
	Mean=	9.111		Mean=	14.311
	SD=	2.604		SD=	4.502
	Description=	Poor		Description=	Average

In the pre-test, 41 of the students or 91.11% of them, almost all of them, show "poor" performance. However, in the post-test, 20 students or 44.44% of them have reduced in "poor" performance, while 15 students or 33.33% and the other 10 or 22.22% have improved to "average" and "high" performances, respectively. The general net increments in these 3 behavioral levels as mentioned above indicate an improvement from the pretest performances to the post-test performances of the Science 10 students.

The mean of 9.111 in the pre-test and 14.311 in the post-test, though the students just read, analyze, and comprehend the module only by themselves without the aid of any other ICT media, the performance of the students reached an average level. These results are supported by earlier studies that claim the students have learned, gained competencies, and improved academic performance from the Printed Modular Learning Delivery where they were under (Lumanta, et. al., 2022, & Nardo, 2017; as cited by Talimadao & Madrigal, 2021).

Test Performances of Students in Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD)

The summary of students' performance in the pre-test and post-test in Science 10 under the Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD) are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Students' Performance in Pre-test and Post-Test under AMLD

Scores	Verbal Description	Pre-test Scores		Post-test Scores	
		F	f%	F	f%
0-12	Poor	30	66.66%	11	24.44%
13-18	Average	15	33.33%	22	48.89%
19-24	High	0	0%	9	20.00%
25-30	Very High	0	0%	3	6.67%
	Mean=	11.227		Mean=	16.222
	SD=	3.564		SD=	4.631
	Description=	Poor		Description=	Average

In the pre-test, 30 of the students or 66.66% of them, most of the student, show "poor" performance. However, in the post-test, 11 students or 24.44% of them have reduced in "poor" performance, while 22 students or 48.89%, then 9 or 20.00% and the other 3 or 6.67% have improved to "average", "high", and very high performances, respectively. The general net increments in these 3 behavioral levels as mentioned above indicate an improvement from the pretest performances to the post-test performances of the Science 10 students.

Furthermore, 9 Students or 20.00% achieved high scores ranging from 19-24 and 3 or 6.67% of them had scored very high with range from 25-30. This means that some of the students who had poor performance had become better with the introduction of audio-visual aid and the printed module (Lapada & Lapada, 2017). Remarking that the utilization of audio-visual aid with the printed module helps students to better comprehend the obscure scientific concepts by themselves (Mastur, 2019 & Shivali, 2022).

Comparison between the Pre-test Performances of Students in PMLD and AMLD

The pre-test performances of students under Printed Modular Learning Delivery and Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery are compared in Table 5.

Table 5. T-test results in the pre-test performances of students between PMLD and AMLD

	Mean	t value	p value	Interpretation	Decision
Group A PMLD	9.111	3.276	0.0015	Significant	Reject Ho ₁
Group B AMLD	11.267				

Note. Significant at the 0.05 level

Group with PMLD and Group with AMLD earned means of 9.111 and 11.267, respectively. These values indicate that both groups perform poorly in the pre-test. The t value of 3.276 and p value of 0.0015 suggest that the performance of students under PMLD and that of students under AMLD are significantly different. These results imply that the pre-test performance of students with AMLD is significantly higher than that of the students with PMLD. This poor performance in the pre-test may be pointed out to the fact that the students have less knowledge yet of the subject matter (Berry, 2008). Having this data, the gained learning of the students could be compared to the results of the post-test to be administered at the end of the learning delivery.

Comparison between the Post-test Performances of Students in PMLD and AMLD

The post-test performances of students under Printed Modular Learning Delivery and Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery are compared in Table 6.

Table 6. T-test results in the post-test performances of students between PMLD and AMLD

	Mean	t value	p value	Interpretation	Decision
Group A	14.311	1.985	0.0503	Not significant	Accept Ho ₂
Group B	16.222				

Note. Significant at the 0.05 level

Group with PMLD and Group with AMLD earned means of 14.311 and 16.222, respectively. These values indicate that both groups perform averagely in the post-test. Despite a little distinction in the mean value, it can be noted that students under AMLD learned better with the use audio-visual (Al Aqad, et. al., 2021). The t value of 1.985 and p value of 0.0503 suggest that the performance of students under PMLD and that of students under AMLD are not significantly different. Although with slight differences in the mean values, these results imply that the post-test performance of students with AMLD does not significantly differ from that of the students with PMLD.

Response of Students Towards AMLD

The response of the students in terms of motivation and interest towards Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD) in

science 10 are tabulated in Table 7.

Table 7. Students' response on Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD) in Science 10 in terms of motivation and interest (n= 45)

ITEMS	Mean	SD	Description
Motivation			
1. It makes the lesson easier to understand.	3.425	0.903	Moderately motivated
2. It intensifies the eagerness of the students.	3.700	0.823	Highly motivated
3. It develops persistence towards understanding the lesson.	3.450	0.986	Moderately motivated
4. It activates excitement to learn more.	4.250	0.981	Highly motivated
5. It arouses curiosity towards the subject matter.	3.675	0.917	Highly motivated
Mean Motivation	3.7		Highly motivated
Interest			
1. It sustains focus in learning.	3.250	1.006	Moderately interested
2. It builds enthusiasm in the topic.	3.500	1.038	Highly interested
3. It develops higher order thinking skills.	4.025	0.920	Highly interested
4. It suits all types of students.	2.875	1.067	Moderately interested
5. It is preferred over Printed modular learning.	3.675	0.997	Highly interested
Mean Interest	3.5		Highly interested

Legend: 1.00-1.45-Least motivated/ interested; 1.46-2.45-Slightly motivated/ interested; 2.46-3.45 -Moderately motivated/ interested; 3.46-4.45-Highly motivated/ interested; 4.46-5.00-Extremely motivated / interested

The utilization of Audio-visual Aided Modular Learning Delivery (AMLD) in Science 10 earned an overall mean of 3.7 for motivation with the description "highly motivated". Item No. 4, which states that "it activates excitement to learn more", had obtained the highest mean of 4.250 describe as "highly motivated" in motivation denoting that the use of audio-visual aid in learning the module leads the students to feel excited to discover more about the topic often. It was followed by Item No. 2, that says "it intensifies the eagerness of the students" with a mean of 3.700 which is also described as often by the Likert Scale. Then, item number 5 with mean of 3.675, described "highly motivated". The item numbers 3 and 1 gaining the lowest means of 3.450 and 3.425, respectively, described to be "moderately motivated".

This implies that the utilization of audio-visual aid with the printed modules influences students' motivational value towards learning. It helps the students in acquiring knowledge, competencies, and skills in learning abstract concepts from the learning modules in Science 10 as the level of motivation among the students is increased (Shivali, 2022 and Mastur, 2019).

Moreover, the items for interest gained an overall mean of 3.5 correspondingly described to be "highly interested". Items numbers 3, 5, and 2 with the statements which describe AMLD to develop higher order thinking skills, preferred over Printed modular learning, and build enthusiasm in the topic, respectively, had gained a mean of 4.025, 3.675, and 5.500 which were described "highly interested". However, items 1 and 4 were considered to have sometimes impacted the interest of the students with the means of 3.250 and 2.875 described to be "moderately motivated". This implies that the interest of students affects the rate of their learning (Alhadabi, 2021; Urhahne & Wijnia, 2023).

Conclusion

This section summarizes the research findings, conclusions, and recommendations made in light of the data examined in the preceding chapter.

Both control (PMLD) and experimental (AMLD) groups show poor performance in the pre-test and average performance in the post-test. The post-test performance of the students under PMLD does not differ significantly from those under the AMLD. The utilization of audio-visual aids (AMLD) in learning Science 10, particularly on the topics of mirrors and lenses, has not demonstrated an advantage over the PMLD. However, the AMLD students' motivation and interest are both high with the utilization of audio-visual aid with the modular learning delivery. This suggests that educators should prioritize these tools to create a more engaging learning environment. Ultimately, fostering a motivated and interested student body can lead to improved learning outcomes and deeper understanding of the material. Based on the summary of findings and conclusion of the study, the use of printed modules amidst aversities should be considered for the continuation of learning though it does not promises remarkable improvement in students' performance it still enables students to understand ideas on their own. Moreover, the incorporation of audio-visual aids might substantially improve this procedure by rendering the courses more captivating and participatory. This combination produces a deeper interest in the subject matter and increases motivation, which together result in a more effective learning environment. By using these techniques, teachers can have the best resources possible to help their pupils through difficult times. however, it is strongly advised that the selection and appropriate combination of audio-visual aids be carefully studied with modules that are printed.

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